

Green and blue space quality: Pre and young teenage girls in urban green and blue spaces

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And

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Executive summary

Access to, and use of, high quality green and blue spaces is associated with numerous health and wellbeing benefits, as well as fostering sense of community and enabling social interaction. Measuring quality, and changes in quality, of green and blue spaces can enable informed management to improve these benefits. Compared to adults, young people are less likely to spend time outdoors, with a widely acknowledged ‘teenage dip’. This decline in use is often higher for females than males. **Understanding how pre and young teenage girls experience green and blue space quality can therefore be important in encouraging continued use.**

This report draws together two research streams. The first used literature reviews and workshops with green and blue space managers and policy makers to identify indicators of green and blue space quality that were of high importance, but not widely used, in Scotland. The second part uses the Girls Outdoors Longitudinal Study, which interviewed pre and young teenage girls from schools across a large urban area about their preferences for green and blue spaces.

Participants in the Girls Outdoors Study were shown outdoor spaces and features informed by these indicators. Themes were identified inductively based on their reactions and discussions, rather than through direct questioning about the indicators themselves. Overall, themes relating to almost all of the high-priority quality indicators identified by practitioners and policymakers in green and blue spaces emerged across the interviews.

- Social interaction was the predominant reason for engaging with green and blue spaces, although for some (though not all), park use is shifting from active play towards walking, chatting, hanging out, and creating photos or videos.
- Accessibility was not discussed in relation to disability as this was not a factor for the participants. Most parks discussed were very local and accessed on foot/bike.
- Aesthetics were most commonly associated with colourful flowers, trees, seasonal colour, healthy vegetation, scenic views, and visual variety.
- Biodiversity elicited mixed reactions, with an identification of “good” biodiversity, such as flowers, butterflies, ducks, birds and frogs, and “bad” biodiversity such as invertebrates with lots of legs.
- Ecological regulation was rarely recognised; the girls tended to prefer clean areas free from litter, not recognising benefits of “messy” nature.
- Water quality was most often recognised visually in relation to preferences for swimming.
- Soil conservation was mentioned only in relation to displeasure for mud.
- Flood risk was mentioned with respect to its impact on aesthetics.

Beyond the priority indicators, participants discussed several features that shaped their engagement with outdoor spaces. These included age-appropriate play equipment, particularly swings and zip lines; clean benches with nearby bins; shelters; attractive views; and paths wide enough to allow groups to walk side by side. Overall, the girls related to outdoor spaces in a strongly sensory, tactile and visceral way, responding to how places felt in the moment rather than to abstract qualities. Their evaluations were shaped by experiences such as comfort, visibility, cleanliness, openness, and how easy it was to move, sit, play, or socialise within a space.

Key messages for management of green and blue outdoor spaces, and for policy:

- There is a mismatch between the indicators that managers do, and would like to, use and the indicators of quality that are important pre and young teenage girls. The additional indicators considered included: physical structure, internal accessibility, recreation, incivilities and services for people.
- Spaces designed to allow for pre and young teenage girls to continue physical exploration of a space, with a variety of natural structures and path types, may encourage continued use. Pre and young teenage girls value the ability to play, climb and move through the physical space of park.
- Measures of green and blue space quality for pre and young teenage girls would benefit from considering social experiences. For this user group, play equipment, particularly swings and ziplines, that are designed for their age and ability are highly desirable. Shelters provide spaces for girls to socialise and escape both the weather and the attention of other park user groups, providing them with some privacy when required.
- Clean and safe spaces are important for pre and young teenage girls' enjoyment of green and blue spaces. This user group want spaces where they will not be bothered by other park users, particularly groups of teenage boys.
- Future data collection with this and other user groups could utilise workshops or focus groups. The use of interviews and photographs enabled a wide range of quality indicators to be discussed, and these to be explored in detail, which may have been missed in more restricted methods. Managers may also wish to consider the use of workshops (perhaps visiting schools to canvas opinions) or focus groups with pre and young teenage girls as a less time-consuming method than interviews to engage with this user group.

Contents

Executive summary	2
Introduction.....	5
Methods	6
Quality indicator results	7
Social interaction	8
Accessibility.....	9
Aesthetics.....	9
Biodiversity	9
Regulation of ecological quality	10
Water quality.....	10
Soil conservation.....	11
Flood risk	12
What makes a good park/outdoor space?.....	13
Additional quality indicators of importance	13
Implications for green and blue space management and policy	15
References	17
Appendix A Photos of different outdoor spaces and features used as prompts	19

Introduction

Access to, and use of, green and blue spaces is associated with numerous health and wellbeing benefits, as well as fostering sense of community and enabling social interaction. However, although access is recognised as important, the *quality* of the spaces accessed may have a larger impact on outcomes (Dobson *et al.*, 2019). Resurfaced footpaths and improved signage, for example, have been linked to increases in physical activity, more social interactions, and increased notice of the environment along a stretch of canal (Benton *et al.*, 2021). Co-created improvements to beach areas (e.g. new play equipment and landscaping) alongside community events were associated with increases in self-reported wellbeing and life satisfaction, mediated by increased feelings of safety and community belonging (van den Bogerd *et al.*, 2021). The Planning (Scotland) Act 2019 requires planning authorities to develop Open Space Strategies, including green and blue spaces. Upcoming Open Space Strategy Regulations include requirements for “advancing equality and eliminating discrimination”. Understanding how groups less engaged with green and blue spaces experience their quality can therefore improve equality in green and blue space use and access.

In order to measure existing quality, understand how to improve quality, and assess impacts of changes to quality, quality indicators are used. However, despite its recognised importance, what is defined as a “quality” green or blue space is often poorly described. Here, we define quality as the ability of a space to deliver benefits (positive outcomes). This may include the physicality of a space (e.g., presence of smooth paths), but also includes how it is embedded in the local area (e.g., transport links), and how the space is used or perceived (e.g., how safe it feels). Quality may vary depending on user group and even within an individual depending on their current needs (e.g., commuting vs socialising vs seeking solitude). Ensuring that quality is maintained or improved for all user groups and use cases can therefore increase the benefits realised from green and blue spaces.

Through a review of literature on green and blue space quality (Roberts *et al.*, 2023) and workshops with green and blue space practitioners and policy makers (Nicholson *et al.*, 2024) we identified priority green and blue space quality indicators for Scotland. This previous work did not, however, explicitly take account of different user groups. In this report we focus on a user group (pre and young teenage girls) where decline in use of green and blue spaces has been observed. We seek to understand how their experience of green and blue space quality compares to the prioritisation of managers and policy makers, and recognise any wider insights into quality they provide.

Compared to adults, young people are less likely to spend time outdoors (Oppliger *et al.*, 2019), with a widely acknowledged ‘teenage dip’ in young people’s engagement in outdoor activities, especially in the early teenage years (Dobson *et al.*, 2019; Richardson *et al.*, 2019). Furthermore, there is a recognised gender gap in engagement with the outdoors (Dobson *et al.*, 2019). Parks and recreational areas are used differently – and generally less often – by girls than boys (Evenson *et al.*, 2016).

While this (female) teenage dip is widely recognised, the reasons for its occurrence are poorly understood. As part of the Scottish Government Strategic Research Program project “Reciprocal Care for Nature”, a longitudinal study – Girls Outdoors – specifically seeks to shed insight on the experience of pre and young teenage girls in different types of outdoor settings. It

utilises a life course perspective which considers the temporal context of behaviour, viewing behaviour from a developmental standpoint, where focus is placed on an individual's unfolding sequence of roles and experiences throughout life and the transition points that mark changes in these roles or states across the study (Elder *et al.*, 2003). Using a life course lens enables an exploration of the points at which, and why, this group (dis)engages with the outdoors, their behaviours in, and their relationship with the outdoors. The Girls Outdoors study therefore seeks to provide in-depth insight and a voice from a group who are seldom the focus of nature-engagement research.

Methods

This report uses data collected as part of the Girls Outdoors study. Here we provide a brief overview of the data collection methods informing that study. For full details please refer to the Girls Outdoors Methods Technical Report (Schulz *et al.*, 2025a).

In the Girls Outdoors study, twenty-four pre-teenage girls were recruited in their final year of primary school (P7, aged 10/11-12) from schools across a large urban area in Scotland. In this longitudinal study, the research team meets with the girls three times over four years in three waves of data collection. In the first wave of data collection a structured interview and a semi-structured "river of life" interview aimed to understand how pre-teen girls were engaging with the outdoors, focusing specifically on green and blue spaces (Schulz *et al.*, 2025b). In the second wave of data collection twenty-one of the original participants (now aged 11-13) revisited their "river of life" interview from wave one, and reflected on changes in their use of outdoor space since then. They were also asked to reflect on aspects of quality of outdoors spaces. In the final wave, the initial structured interview questions will be re-explored alongside the semi-structured "river of life" exploration of change in outdoor (dis)engagement.

It is data from the second wave that forms the basis of this report. Specifically, we draw upon open-ended questions that guided the "river of life" discussion, including:

- How are you using outdoor space now compared to last year?
- What has triggered these changes in how you use different types of outdoor space?
- What do you like or dislike about the outdoor spaces you visit?
- What makes a good park?

The second wave included an optional photo-elicitation task in which girls photographed outdoor places and features that were meaningful in their everyday lives. Instructions were deliberately open-ended, enabling participants to capture spaces they enjoyed, avoided, or felt could be improved. During the interview, participants selected up to ten photographs for discussion.

Researchers also introduced a set of curated images representing a range of outdoor spaces and features, and suggestive of particular quality indicators (Appendix A), informed by findings from Wave 1. These images were used to prompt discussion of participants' likes, dislikes, and ideas for improving outdoor environments. Interviews were guided by a modified SHOWD framework (Langhout, 2014), focusing on what participants saw, how spaces related to their

daily lives, why they were experienced positively or negatively, and what changes might enhance them.

Within the context of this particular study, transcripts from the Girls Outdoors interviews were content-analysed and statements relating to **eight**¹ **specific quality indicators**, as well as quality in general, were extracted, collated and summarised. The specific quality indicators explored in the Girls Outdoors study were drawn from the output of a literature review (Roberts *et al.*, 2023) and stakeholder workshops (Nicholson *et al.*, 2024) which identified 72 potential indicators of green and blue space quality that could be used in Scotland. The eight quality indicators were identified as being of both high importance and not currently used, and included:

- Social interaction
- Accessibility – getting to the site
- Aesthetics
- Biodiversity
- Regulation of ecological quality
- Water quality
- Soil conservation
- Flood risk

The summary findings and implications drawn are presented in the following sections:

- Quality results – Here we set out how the girls’ discussion related to the specific quality indicators identified as high importance and high preference for use in Scotland and which form the basis of a report for policy and practice (Roberts *et al.*, 2026).
- Implications for green and blue space management and policy – This section discusses the wider lessons learned in relation to quality as experienced by pre and young teenage girls, and how this may be incorporated into policy or management.

Quality indicator results

In this section themes from the girls’ interviews that relate to the priority indicators are discussed. Each indicator is considered in turn, with a definition of the indicator provided at the start of each sub-section. Following consideration of each indicator, we discuss what makes a good park, from the girls’ point of view.

¹ Although nine quality indicators were identified as being of high importance in the stakeholder workshops, in the research reported here, we have considered **Accessibility – site access** and **Accessibility – disability** together under the heading Accessibility, as disability was not a factor for any of the participants in the Girls Outdoors study.

Social interaction

Indicator definition:

Green and blue spaces can be designed to facilitate social interaction, through the design of their paths, presence of facilities such as cafes, or layout of benches. Additionally social interaction may be encouraged through activities or other social interventions happening within the green or blue space.

The majority of comments regarding social interaction are positive – girls this age use parks and green and blue spaces as a primary place for socialising with their friends. The activities they take part in in parks are starting to change – for some, but not all – from active play to walking and hanging out. For example:

Interviewer: Uh-huh, so [you] go to the park with your friends and what do you do?

Girl: We get some food and then like eat, then after a little bit then we play in the park.

Interviewer: What kind of games do you play?

Girl: It's not really games; it's just like we play on the swings. (Poppy, 2025)

Some of the girls do not like to be alone in parks and outdoor spaces, while others are more comfortable with this. There is, however, general agreement that busy parks can be intimidating, especially if older (and male) children/adults are there. This has led to some places that used to be frequented now being avoided in certain circumstances:

Parent: But you won't go to the playground because the boys are playing football, right?

Girl: Yeah, and I'm scared to go there by myself because there might be older boys and I'm kind of scared around older boys. It's just very scary. (Brittany, 2025)

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Girl: There's not really places...well, there's some places that I maybe used to go but I don't really go any more, because the people there are like... they've become more littered. I used to go up to Allerton Drive, but there's normally boys there doing random, stupid things.

Interviewer: So you've just stopped going completely?

Girl: Yeah, kind of, because it was in P7 when I used to go there, and then it was in P7 that I started finding that whenever I went there, there was boys on electric scooters, jumping in the river.

Interviewer: And does that make you feel uncomfortable?

Girl: Yeah, kind of, just because they're very loud and shouty. (Katy, 2025)

Accessibility

Indicator definition:

Getting to the site, like accessibility for disability, impacts who is able to access the benefits of visiting green and blue spaces. Sites which can be accessed via safe, well-lit walking paths or public transport will be more open to a wider variety of visitors.

The girls mainly accessed local park and green and blue spaces on foot or by bike. Where transport was involved they usually travelled with a family member by car or public transport. For the girls, comments and reflections around accessibility topics mainly focused on the width and surfaces of the paths within the parks they visit.

Aesthetics

Indicator definition:

The visual look of a green or blue space can impact users' enjoyment. Aesthetics may relate to the natural features, such as the view or colour of flowers, but can also include negative aspects, such as bordering busy roads or graffiti.

When asked what they like about the photographs of different areas within a green or blue space, or what would make those areas (and parks in general) better, flowers and trees were frequently mentioned. Colourful flowers are very popular with this demographic, both for their visual appearance and for pollinators. The girls are also keen on views, and appreciated the outdoor location where it looked like a good view could be achieved, for example, Photo 3 (path to cliffs).

However, it is important to acknowledge that positive aesthetics alone were not always enough to attract the girls to spend time in an outdoor place if there was nothing to do. The play/activity potential of an outdoor space was the key motivation in finding it appealing.

The girls were sensitive to negative aesthetic aspects such as litter and graffiti.

Biodiversity

Indicator definition:

Biodiversity includes all of the living things, including plants, and animals, but also small or microscopic organisms such as fungi or bacteria. Biodiversity in particular refers to the difference types of organisms, as well as the number of each that can be found. Improving biodiversity is often a key tenant of creating or maintaining green and blue spaces, particularly for above ground plants and animals.

While the girls do not explicitly talk about biodiversity or explicitly express value judgements around places based on the variety of plant or animal life, some are attracted to places where they could see nature, or that are more nature rich (for example, deer, seals, flowers, trees, butterflies etc.)

While there are many positive comments made towards flowers, trees, bees, butterflies, birds and mammals, some girls have phobias of birds, bugs and “insects with lots of legs”. For some there is a clear visceral response to encountering some of these creatures:

Also centipedes are weird looking, they have 100 legs. Millipedes are chill because they just curl into a ball... And then they're... cute. (Lola, 2025)

Both positive and negative attitudes to and understanding of biodiversity is demonstrated. For example, wild/flowers are seen as positive for pollinators, yet flowers and plants can also be disliked for being spiky, prickly and hosting insects.

Oh I like it as well. I'd cut back the bushes and so you could walk by without being... stabbed by flowers [laughs]. (Detina, 2025)

Regulation of ecological quality

Indicator definition:

Green and blue spaces are linked to wider ecological networks. These ecological networks work in balance with each other, impacting ecological functioning beyond individual components of a space. For example, riparian woodlands may reduce soil erosion which maintains water quality, with consequences for downstream fishes.

Some girls express displeasure about litter, engage in litter picks and are aware of the negative impact litter can have on wildlife. However, considerations related to the ecological functions of these features did not emerge in the girls' discussions. For example, deadwood was not described in terms of its ecological benefits; spiky marram grass was sometimes viewed as an obstacle to play (e.g. jumping down sand dunes); and while participants expressed a strong interest in climbable trees, some favoured the removal of trees they perceived as less appealing:

Girl: Ooh, I love the flowers and the way the whole scenery looks. The tree's kind of annoying me though, that's right there. It's a bit wonky. It's kind of like in the way of going through the path. Maybe if they just moved the tree just...

Parent: They're not gonna do that.

Girl: They could just cut it down and add a new one. (Brittany, 2025, reaction to Photo 8, riverside)

In the quote above, the flowers to which the girl refers are those of Himalayan Balsam. None of the girls identified this as an invasive species and comments were positive about the pretty appearance of the flowers.

Water quality

Indicator definition:

Water quality can include water found within the green or blue space, as well as water that might be extracted for drinking or other uses (e.g., agriculture). Water quality may directly impact users (e.g., illness from coming into contact with poor quality water) or may impact through things such as sight or smell.

Water quality for the girls was primarily referenced through its visual appearance. Some voiced suspicions over the cleanliness of the brown water in Photo 8 (riverside), relating the brown colour to dirt and voicing a preference for clear water.

One girl, interpreting the photo as of a pond rather than a river, made a distinction between how different bodies of water 'clean themselves':

Interviewer: Okay. Would you go into the water?

Girl: No. It doesn't look very clean. I don't know what's been in that water as well. It's like the ocean, which is kind of like cleaning itself, but this is just like a wee pond so it's like no things coming out and in so it's kind of just like, just draining itself out, I guess. (Julia, 2025)

For the girls, water quality was also related to what might, or might not, be in the water:

Girl: It looks a little bit muddy, from like the camera but I always test the water before I go in. I quite like going in lakes as well I'd have to make sure it was at least clean-ish.

Interviewer: So you would go in with your feet to test the water?

Girl: I'd probably use my hand if I can see visibly, dirt...

Interviewer: ...you wouldn't go in?

Girl: Probably not because you don't know what could be in the water. (Detina, 2025)

There was also a particular fear of seaweed, and the way it feels:

Parent: Would you have gone in it? I sometimes wonder how clean the River Farr is, to be honest!

Girl: Sometimes seaweed does travel, I get the sense...

Parent: Seaweed! You don't like seaweed touching you.

Girl: Yeah, it feels weird. [makes shuddering sound] (Amy, 2025)

Soil conservation

Indicator definition:

Soil conservation can impact across uses of green and blue spaces. Soil erosion can reduce access and visual appeal, lead to de-stabilisation and raise safety concerns, as well as impacting things such as water quality or depth.

The girls rarely mentioned soil unless they were referring to mud, which they generally disliked and wished to avoid. One photo in particular (Photo 6, muddy path) was met with general dismay and negative comments about the ‘squelchiness’ of the mud. Participants often referred to walking around the edges of the mud, on the grass; there were no comments acknowledging the soil erosion that might result from this practice.

Interviewer: So, if you went for a walk and you came across this path, would you turn back?

Girl: No, I mean if it was the quickest way, I'd probably just like walk on the green bits and like try my best just to walk not in the like road...

Interviewer: Okay, yeah. So, you would try and avoid the muddy bits?

Girl: Yes. (Julia, 2025, in response to Photo 6, muddy path)

In her description of what would make a good park, one girl distinguished between muddy grass, ‘good’ grass and fake grass:

Okay, so, swings – not the baby swings, a bigger slide, more like...you know, not like muddy grass, good grass- not fake grass. (Bambie, 2025)

Flood risk

Indicator definition

Flood risk can impact the functioning and safety of the green or blue space for users, as well as their access. Further it may impact green and blue spaces’ ability to deliver other benefits, such as improved water quality, or impact aesthetics even after the flood event has passed.

The flood risk element depicted in Photo 6 (muddy path) was not commented upon by the girls, who only commented on the mud. The only photo that prompted comments about flooding was Photo 5 (gulls on a flooded playing field):

It looks very wet. It doesn't look like there's...like it's meant to be, like it just looks like it's kind of flooded. I mean it still looks like... if it wasn't flooded, that would look like a nice place to go. Like, I would... personally, I'd remove the seagulls and the water. (Josie, 2025)

And then that water on the grass doesn't make it look as pretty, having some pathways and drains and stuff like that, yeah. (Detina, 2025)

What makes a good park/outdoor space?

Desirable features of parks include (clean) benches with bins nearby, shelters, views, and paths that are broad enough for groups to walk side-by-side. Space that allows for free movement and speed (for example for gymnastics and running games) as well as providing bushes and trees for hide and seek are requested. Climbable trees and lots of flowers are highly desirable. Places that offer potential for many different activities are valued.

This age group of girls relate to the qualities of an outdoor place in a sensory, visceral way. They are sensitive to mud (“*too squelchy*”) and dirt and human-made negative impacts on quality such as litter and graffiti.

Because most of the benches there are quite disgusting. They've got like cigarettes on them, or like some poo or... (Julia, 2025)

They also highlighted specific tactile elements of nature, such as plants (“*bugs live in plants*”), spiders, and water:

I still don't like touching the spiders though. Because...well, I don't like accidentally squashing them because then there's...bug juice on me (Lola, 2025)

I don't like puddles like that where you can't actually walk without getting splashed or scratched (Lola, 2025).

The girls value the twisty, tactile appearance of trees or rocks that are good for climbing.

This would be a good tree to climb. It was behind a fence, so I couldn't climb it, but that...do you see what I mean? The twisty branches? (Tigger, 2025)

At the same time, however, the girls do not enjoy being scraped or poked by overgrown plants

The plants, I don't like plants that touch my legs. I don't like overgrown walkways because then my legs get scratched (Lola, 2025).

In general, this age group of girls want play equipment of an appropriate size and challenge level for them, particularly swings and ziplines.

I think I'm getting a bit big for the normal swings now. My waist is getting bigger and I don't like that (Brittany, 2025)

Additional quality indicators of importance

As well as the priority quality indicators included in the toolkit (Roberts *et al.* 2026), the girls' interviews revealed several additional indicators of quality of importance to them. Although these additional quality indicators were not those recognised as of highest priority amongst practitioners and policy makers who took part in our research, they did all appear in the

validated index of green and blue space quality developed from literature and workshops (Nicholson *et al.*, 2024). The indicators identified included:

- **Physical structure** (for example, forest or terrain structure)
- **Accessibility – internal** (accessibility within the green or blue space, such as paths)
- **Recreation** – non-sports facilities
- **Incivilities** (for example, graffiti, vandalism, dog fouling, litter)
- **Services – people** (non-recreational services that enable people to use the space)

Although none of these indicators were identified as of highest importance by managers and policy makers, two – **physical structure** and **internal accessibility** – were both identified as important by practitioners/policy makers. Of these, **physical structure** was recognised as already in use, while **accessibility** was of interest to use. Although the other three indicators were classed as least important, **non-sport recreation facilities** was identified as something managers and policy makers were interested to use. Both **incivilities** and **services – people** however were not identified as wanting to be used.

Physical structure was discussed most often by the participants in this study in terms of wanting trees or rocks to climb or sit on, or appropriate places to create dens, as well as picnic spots and places to play hide and seek. Their interest in physical structure is often tactile, and they have a desire to move through and interact with the whole space, beyond the man-made structures provided. To maintain use by teenage girls, managers may therefore seek to facilitate access to natural features of spaces, or, where not appropriate, design features which meet the need for climbing and building suited to teenage use, not only younger children. With regards to **internal accessibility**, the participants exclusively discussed paths. Here variation in preferences is seen, with preferences shown for wide paths for socialising, natural paths in natural areas, and flat paths to facilitate scootering.

Preferences for **non-sport recreation facilities** included ziplines and swings, specifically those designed to accommodate teenage body shapes and sizes, with appropriate levels of physical challenge. While ziplines link to the physical interaction with the space seen in preferences for **physical structure**, discussions of swings overlapped with **social interaction**, as swings were places to sit and talk as much as move. Social seating in the form of benches was also highlighted as important, falling here under the indicator **services – people**. With relation to **incivilities** participants wished for spaces to get away from rowdy park users, mentioning groups of boys and men in particular. Spaces free of graffiti (**incivilities**) and with enough bins (**services – people**) were also highlighted as important. Like many park users, pre and young teenage girls consider high quality spaces to be clean and free of graffiti, however they take this further to specifically refer to spaces that are not just clean but are attractive and feel safe for them to engage in different activities.

Implications for green and blue space management and policy

Following on from these observations, we draw out the following key messages:

Key message

There is a mismatch between the indicators that managers do, and would like to, use and the indicators of quality that are important to pre and young teenage girls.

Overall, the themes raised in the interviews cover almost all of the high priority quality indicators identified by practitioners and policy makers in green and blue space (Nicholson *et al.*, 2024). However, the interviews made clear that there are several additional quality indicators that are important to pre and young teenage girls. These include:

- Physical structure
- Accessibility – internal
- Recreation
- Incivilities
- Services – people

Key message

Spaces designed to allow for pre and young teenage girls to continue physical exploration of a space, with a variety of natural structures and path types, may encourage continued use

Pre and young teenage girls value the ability to play, climb and move through the physical space of park. They value trees and rocks that are good for climbing. Managers could consider whether installation of natural playground equipment such as mounds, boulders and tree trunks (both to sit on and for climbing) could help encourage continued use of parks by this user group.

Key message

Measures of green and blue space quality for pre and young teenage girls would benefit from considering social experiences

Social interaction is very important to this user group. The provision of spaces for girls to play and hang out is key to maintaining their engagement with parks. For this user group, play equipment, particularly swings and ziplines, that are designed for their age and ability are highly desirable. Shelters provide spaces for girls to socialise and escape both the weather and the attention of other park user groups, providing them with some privacy when required.

Related to this is the desire for safe spaces.

Key message

Clean and safe spaces are important for pre and young teenage girls' enjoyment of green and blue spaces

This user group want spaces where they will not be bothered by other park users, particularly groups of teenage boys.

Finally, we consider the methodological challenges of collecting data from pre and young teenage girls.

Key message

Future data collection with this and other user groups could utilise workshops or focus groups

The use of interviews and photographs enabled a wide range of quality indicators to be discussed, and these to be explored in detail, which may have been missed in more restricted methods. However, interviews are time consuming and expensive, including preparation time, ethics considerations, interview, transcription, and analysis, as well as requiring skilled interviewers. To overcome this, managers that want to pay specific attention for quality for pre and young teenage girls may design data collection to focus specifically on those elements of quality, particularly social connection and tactile/sensory experience, which this research has highlighted as particularly important for this user group. Managers may also wish to consider the use of workshops (perhaps visiting schools to canvas opinions) or focus groups with pre and young teenage girls as a less time-consuming method than interviews to engage with this user group.

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Appendix A Photos of different outdoor spaces and features used as prompts

Photo 1: **Biodiversity** – wildflowers, different tree species, deer

Photo 2: **Regulation of ecological quality / lack of biodiversity** – empty space with few species

Photo 3: **Accessibility** – access to outdoor spaces (a more remote outdoor location outside the city)

Photo 4: **Accessibility** – facilities within outdoor spaces

Photo 5: **Flood risk** – flooded greenspace

Photo 6: **Soil conservation** – muddy path

Photo 7 - **Water quality** – blue space (beach and sea)

Photo 8 - **Water quality:** blue space (river and vegetation)

Photo 9 - **Aesthetics** – a “messy” part of a park

Photo 10 - **Aesthetics** – a “tidy” part of a park